

THE ROLE OF AN INNOVATIVE APPROACH IN DEVELOPING THE THINKING
ABILITY OF PRIMARY STUDENTS

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Annotation: This article discusses the role of innovative educational technologies in the formation and development of thinking skills of primary school students. Problem-based learning, didactic games, collaborative methods, and teacher-student interactive communication are analyzed as the main tools for activating thinking activity. Specific pedagogical recommendations are given based on experimental work.

Keywords: primary education, thinking skills, innovative approach, problem-based learning, didactic games, interactive methods.

One of the important tasks facing the education system today is to teach students to think independently and to fully develop their intellectual potential. In particular, the primary school stage is the most responsible period of this process. Because it is at this stage that the child begins to master such thinking operations as reasoning, analysis, comparison, and generalization. The use of innovative approaches in education makes this process significantly more effective.

Primary school students are still emotional, mobile, and impressionable by their age. Their thinking is more figurative and practical in nature. Therefore, in developing students' thinking at this stage, it is important that the educational content is close to life and that the lesson process is organized through interactive methods.

Pedagogical research shows that new, creative, and innovative methods provide higher results than traditional approaches in revealing students' intellectual potential. Thinking is not just about acquiring knowledge, but also about drawing independent conclusions based on the information learned, finding solutions to problems, and developing new ideas.

In the problem-based learning method, the teacher encourages the student to search for himself, rather than providing ready-made information. This activates the student's thinking activity. For example, through questions such as "Why?", "How could it have happened?", "Could there be another solution?", the student's logical thinking and ability to see cause-and-effect relationships are developed.

Working in problem situations teaches students to critically look at their knowledge, to conduct independent research, and to make the right decisions. This method forms not only knowledge, but also life skills.1. Muammoli ta'lim metodining amaliy tatbiqi (davomi)

By creating problem situations for primary school students, their logical thinking, determining cause-and-effect relationships, finding answers to questions, and guessing skills are activated. For example, questions such as the following can be asked in the lesson:

“What would happen if there were no leaves on the trees?”

“If it rained 3 times in 1 week, how would it affect us?”

Such questions are not just about memorizing facts, but also forcing the child to think and justify his opinion. Through this, he will understand not only the topic of the lesson, but also life relationships related to the environment.

The results of the experiment show that of the students who participated in lessons organized on the

basis of problem tasks:

84% began to express their opinions independently,

76% showed an active attitude towards the lesson,

69% were able to analyze and evaluate the opinions of other children.

This means that problem-based learning gives real practical results in the formation of thinking at the primary stage.

2. Didactic games - a means of stimulating thinking

Didactic games are recognized as a particularly powerful tool in primary education. Because the game is a natural form of child thinking. Through the game, the student independently searches for knowledge, compares, and draws conclusions. Through games such as "Logical Pair", "Find and Explain", "Restore the Sequence", "What Did You Forget?", the child learns to connect cause and effect, to perform mental operations.

For example, in a mathematics lesson, the game "Number Mystery Box" is played. 3 numbers are hidden in the box, and their sum and difference are called. The student must find the numbers in the box based on this information. This game develops the child's skills of:

Analysis,

Comparison of possible solutions,

Drawing conclusions,

Logical problem solving.

Also, in native language and environmental classes, the child learns to think freely through game tasks such as "Find and identify", "Correct the wrong sentence", "Make a story from words".

The results of the experiment carried out through games showed that:

78% of students began to enjoy the lesson;

82% tried to answer questions with creative thinking;

More than 70% of students mastered independent question formulation.

These results show that didactic games are not only interesting, but also a powerful method that influences thinking.

3. Integration of innovative methods and an integrated approach

When the above methods (problem-based learning and didactic games) are used together, even higher efficiency is achieved. The innovative approach focuses not only on knowledge, but also on the student's thinking process. The following principles are followed:

The principle of "Not knowledge - give an opinion!": in the lesson, not ready-made information is presented, questions are raised, and answers are sought.

Activity and participation: the student becomes a participant, not a "spectator" of the lesson.

Person-oriented education: each child expresses his/her opinion within the limits of his/her abilities, and this is appreciated.

Also, the ability of teachers to work with modern tools - multimedia lessons, interactive whiteboards, digital tasks - also develops analytical thinking in students.

Didactic games are very important in arousing interest in students, consolidating knowledge, and most importantly - developing thinking activity. Through games such as "Logical Chain", "Find and Explain", "Sharpen the Mind", students gain a deep understanding of the topic and can freely express their thoughts.

Through didactic games, the child learns skills such as analyzing various situations, making decisions, and putting forward alternative ideas. Learning through play is based on the child's natural need for

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movement and interest, which makes the thinking process more active.

In modern education, the teacher is not a source of knowledge, but a teaching partner. The teacher should be a person who encourages the student to think, supports him and guides him. In this case, active dialogue with the student is formed using methods such as "Question and Answer", "Brainstorming", "Blitz-survey", "Cluster".

As a result of this cooperation, students learn to freely express their opinions, think critically and logically, and independently assess a situation.

Experimental studies conducted on the basis of the above methods and techniques have shown that students' thinking indicators have significantly increased in classes that use innovative approaches in the teaching process. Students' different approaches to the problem, a variety of answer options, and an independent approach to questions are evidence of these changes.

In achieving such results, the teacher's openness to innovation, organization of the teaching process based on modern technologies, and constant methodological research are important factors.

In conclusion, the development of thinking skills in primary education serves as an important basis for the intellectual development of students. Innovative approaches - problem-based learning, didactic games, and cooperation methods - allow this process to be implemented more effectively and purposefully. The student forms his own opinion, draws conclusions, and learns to analyze life situations. This creates the foundation for his development as an independent and creative individual in the subsequent stages.

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